

ADMINISTRATIVE STRUCTURE AND MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES OF THE STATE OF AMIR TEMUR

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Abstract: the administrative structure of the state of Amir Temur and the management system in state activities were analyzed based on historical sources.

Key words: Amir Temur, Suyurgatmish Khan, Sultan Mahmud Khan, Kazan Khan, Saray Mulk Khanim, Jahangir Mirza, Mironshah Mirza, Shahrukh Mirza, Pir Muhammed Mirza, Rustam Mirza, Abu Bakr Mirza, Sayyid Baraka, Mir Sayyid Sharif Jurjani, Ala-al property, Abu-l-Maoli, Ali Akbar, Movarounahrda, Balkh, Khurasan, Kabul, Ghazna, Kandahar, Indian lands, Isfahan, Baghdad.

Introduction

When Amir Temur Movarounnahr ascended the throne, the situation in the country was very difficult. The region of Movarounnahr had not yet completely recovered from the problems of the Mongol invasion, the national economy was in ruins, and the hardworking people were going through hard times. Restoration of the economy, which is the basis of state power, establishment of political and administrative institutions was one of the first main tasks that Amir Temur had to solve as a ruler.

The main part

After Amir Temur ascended the Movarounnahr throne in May 1370, he ended the feudal disunity in the country and founded a single centralized great state, but he did not declare himself the "legitimate" khan of this state. Because he did not belong to the Genghis dynasty in terms of lineage. Therefore, following the tradition of the Chigatai people, he first made Suyurgatmish Khan (1370-1388), and after his death, Sultan Mahmud Khan (1388-1402), the son of Suyurgatmish Khan, in his presence. till the end of his life, he issued labels, gave orders and minted money on their behalf. Both of these khans did not interfere in the political life of the state with the orders given by Amir Temur. Nevertheless, in order to strengthen his political position, Amir Temur married Sarai Mulk, daughter of Kazan Khan, one of the Mongol Khans. Thanks to this marriage in 1370, Amir Temur got the title "kuragon", that is, "son-in-law of the khan". This was one of the traditions required from the rulers of the kingdom according to the laws of that time. This is how Sahibqiron was called "Amir Temur Kuragon" in official documents.

Amir Temur's kingdom was administratively divided into uluses, which in turn were divided into regions and districts. The entrepreneur relied on his relatives to manage the country. The western regions of the country were given to the middle son Mironshah, the Balkh region to the eldest son Jakhangir Mirza, and the youngest son Shahrukh Mirza of Khurasan. He also gave his grandchildren a gift. In particular, the lands of Kabul, Azna, Kandahar, and Hind were given to Pir Muhammed, Isfahan to Rustam, the son of Umarshaikh, and Abu Bakr, the son of Mironshah of Baghdad.

Amir Temur's first step towards the establishment of an independent centralized state was to completely free it from the Mongols and introduce new and perfect rules and regulations in the management of the kingdom. Although the state founded by Amir Temur did not differ much from the sovereign states that ruled in the Muslim East typical of the Middle Ages, the management systems in the kingdom were improved by the age-old traditions of the ancient Turan-Turkistan statehood and new rules and laws. A vivid example of this is Temur's rule. In the regulations created by the founders, strict procedures and laws were developed about state management, administrative officials and their duties, and the role of various social categories in the life of the society.

The central administration of the state of Amir Temur was managed by the prime minister - the head of the devanbeg, the archon of seven ministries - the state council of ministers. The first ministry was in charge of country and official affairs. This ministry dealt with harvests, taxes, tributes and their distribution, income and expenses, and beautification works collected from the districts of the region. The second one was the minister of sipoh, i.e., he was in charge of military affairs and was involved in the provision of soldiers' salaries, food and weapons. The third is the Ministry of Commerce, which is responsible for collecting zakat and duties from the property of merchants, disposing of property left without owners, and solving issues related to inheritance and heirs. The fourth is the minister of affairs of the kingdom, that is, the minister of financial affairs, who managed the expenses from the state treasury and the income and expenses of the kingdom in general. In addition to these four ministries, three more special ministries were established to supervise the affairs of border regions and subordinate countries. These three ministers were involved in the control of revenues from these regions to the state treasury and related financial issues. They, in turn, formed the main supervisory board of the kingdom. This committee is called "kholisa". These seven ministries were subordinated to the devanbeg, and in coordination with him, they carried out important financial affairs of the kingdom.

The dargah in the palace - a special council - also played an important role in state administration. This council discussed the most important issues of domestic and foreign policy, the appointment of officials to the highest functions of power, and other issues. Arzbegi, tovachi, khajib, jibachi, qushbegi, treasurer, khans, bakovulbashi, secretary, munshi, bitikchi and other palace officials worked in the dargah system.

In the state offices of Amir Temur, decrees were introduced in a unique new way - the sarnama method. This method represented Amir Temur as a ruler. The requirements set by Amir Temur on the procedure for issuing decrees were also accepted by his descendants. This is based on many documents issued by a number of Timurid rulers, such as Shahrukh Mirza and Abu Said Mirza, and preserved in their original copies.

One of the great things that Amir Temur did was to establish and defend the idea of statehood as a free and civilized institution. Amir Temur kept the administrative divisions introduced by Kebak Khan (1318 - 1326) in Movarounnahr and appointed new thousands and district heads to these divisions. He introduced new and perfect procedures in the management of the kingdom.

Amir Temur widely used the experiences of political management in the past in building his state. According to its structural structure, this state was often based on military and political systems. His system of state administration was built on the basis of a unified centralized political order in the entire territory under his control, and the experiences in this field were

enriched by the experience of administrative methods widely used in the Central Asian states of the Middle Ages. Amir Temur's extensive use of the work "Siyasatnoma" created by Nizamulmuluk as a guide in state affairs, and the use of ideas from "Siyasatnoma" in "Temur's Constitutions" are a vivid example of this.

Amir Temur followed the eight principles of statehood that existed before him:

- the state should be politically independent;
- that the state and society are managed on the basis of certain laws, procedures, and ideology;
- rules coordinating the management system have been formed;
- social and economic relations in the society should be under the state's attention;
- constant concern about the development of science and culture;
- according to the conditions and procedures of each period, to carry out the issues of the internal development of the state and society using the existing factors in the external world;
- the powers at the top of the state understand the past, present and future with deep thinking, strong faith, extremely high spirituality and nationalism.

Amir Temur added the ninth to these foundations of statehood, the development of society and the provision of interests of all social classes. During this period, the administration consisted of two offices: the dargah and the ministry (devan), and the dargah was headed by the supreme ruler. The Supreme Council was responsible for managing the activity of the Dargah, its communication with the councils and local authorities.

Amir Temur's service in history is that he improved the management system of statehood, internal and foreign policy procedures, and legal foundations in the new historical conditions. He had a thousand footmen, a thousand camels, and a thousand horsemen who were aware of external and internal emergencies. Special stations - shelters were established throughout the whole kingdom within a day's journey. 50-200 head of horses were caught at each station.

Amir Temur also widely used the advice of his peers in the affairs of the kingdom. "Temur's Laws" contains a description of the owner's pirs and their instructions. Zainuddin Abubakr Toyabadi, a great sheikh originally from Khorasan, advised Amir Temur to follow the principles of council, consultation, prudence and prudence in state administration.

Also, the active participation of Sayyid Baraka, Mir Sayyid Sharif Jurjani, Ala-al Mulk, Abu-l-Maoli and Ali Akbar from the Sayyids of Termiz in the councils in the dargahs of Amir Temur's state is described in "Temur's Laws". In the state administration, businessmen worked based on Islamic laws. His attitude towards the Holy Qur'an and Hadith Sharif was sincere and at a high level. He had unlimited respect for the descendants of the Prophet, Sheikhs-ul-Mashayikhs. He relied on such people to strengthen the state. In the studies of the years of independence, Amir Temur stated that in the activities of statehood, the interrelationship of the central and local government agencies, the rules of subordination to each other were regulated, the balance between form and content was ensured, which led to the creation of a high communication system in the country. It was emphasized that Amir Temur strengthened this system with capable, knowledgeable and spiritually mature specialists. Also, it was shown that the congresses played an important role in the country's management and development, that during the time of Amir Temur, the judicial and law enforcement sectors were specialized, and this sector served as the support of the state. that the internal and external threats that may be caused by it have been eliminated in time and developed measures to prevent them; that he served to predict stability in the kingdom, to achieve his goals in the

Asian region, to accelerate the integration processes, that Amir Temur organized his foreign campaigns primarily to end oppression, injustice, and tyranny, he tried to ensure the well-being of the people in the regions, and he fought for the strength of the Islamic religion and Sharia justified.

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